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Effects of HRM practices, lean production practices and lean duration on performance

Abstract

The purpose of this research is to investigate the structural relationships between HRM practices, lean production practices, operational performance and firm performance of manufacturing firms that have implemented lean production. The data were collected from the firms operating in Sri Lanka, which fulfilled the selection criteria set for the study. Statistical techniques were used to test the hypothesized relationships. It was found that lean production practices and operational performance mediate the relationship between HRM practices and firm performance; lean duration moderates the relationship between HRM practices and lean production practices in such a way that the longer the duration, the greater would be the adoption of lean production practices. The essential contribution of the findings lie in presenting empirical data valuable for the advancement of research in HRM as well as for making decisions on people management when implementing advanced manufacturing technologies.

Key words: lean production; human resource management; leanness; operational performance; lean duration, firm performance.

Introduction

There is a growing recognition of the pivotal role of advanced manufacturing approaches in responding to global competition (Bamber, Stanton, Bartram, & Ballardie, 2014). Particularly salient among these is lean production. The core thrust of adopting lean production is the elimination of waste and non-value-added activities to create a streamlined, high quality system that enhances operational performance, ultimately yielding competitive advantage (Birdi et al., 2008; de Koeijer, Paauwe, & Huijsman, 2014). To date, lean production has been extensively applied to organizations spanning large to small-sized in traditional manufacturing to non-traditional white collar settings worldwide (García, Maldonado,

Alvarado, & Rivera, 2014; Kollberg, Dahlgaard, & Brehmer, 2007; Tortorella, Marodin, Fogliatto, & Miorando, 2015).

However, organizations fail to make a sustainable transition to advanced manufacturing systems when changes in the manufacturing function do not accompany complementary changes in human resource management (HRM) practices. It is argued that human resources are managed in ways inconsistent with the requirements of advanced manufacturing systems (Agarwal, Green, Brown, Tan, & Randhawa, 2013; Bortolotti, Boscari, & Danese, 2015; Cullinane, Bosak, Flood, & Demerouti, 2014; Losonci, Demeter and Jenei, 2011; Tracey and Flinchbaugh, 2006). For instance, Losonci et al. (2011) state that the introduction of a wide range of new principles and methods of lean production radically changes the way operations are carried out at the shop-floor. Agarwal et al. (2013) and Tracey and Flinchbaugh (2006) provide evidence for a lack of alignment between HRM strategy and the aims of lean implementation. Hence, consistency is needed between different organizational strategies that are introduced to ensure successful deployment of organizational resources (e.g. technological and human).

Previous studies on the one hand, support the contention that bundles of complementary HRM practices outperform individual best practices in enhancing firm performance (e.g., Subramony, 2009). On the other hand, previous studies suggest the importance of HRM bundles in influencing the successful implementation of lean production (e.g., Birdi et al., 2008; Sakakibara, Flynn, Schroeder and Morris, 1997; Zacharatos, Hershcovis, Turner, & Barlin, 2007); the firms that combined lean production practices with HRM practices outperformed the firms that did not do so (de Menezes, Wood, & Gelade, 2010; MacDuffie, 1995; Zu & Fredendall, 2009). However, it is very rare to find empirical studies on transition of firms to advanced manufacturing systems and the adoption of HRM practices to facilitate such transitions. As a result, there is no consensus on which HRM practices ought to be incorporated to facilitate the transition. Therefore, the literature has yet to address the ways in which HRM practices and lean production could be integrated in order to create the necessary conditions for successful implementation of lean production to yield positive results at the operational and firm-levels.

In the above context, the main objective of our study is to investigate the structural relationships between HRM practices, lean production practices, operational performance and firm performance of manufacturing firms that had implemented lean production in Sri Lanka. It is expected that the findings of our study will provide valuable information to clearly apprehend the contribution of HRM practices in the adoption of lean production in enhancing performance at the operational and firm-levels. The essential contribution of our research lies in presenting empirical data valuable for the advancement of the literature as well as for making informed strategic decisions. Consistent with the objective, the article is organised as

follows. The next section reviews, in brief, the theoretical background of the study. Thereafter, the methodology used in this empirical study is presented. Results are then presented and discussed, and finally conclusions and discussion of implications are presented.

Literature review and hypotheses development

Lean production

Lean production centres on the elimination of waste and the creation of value (Womack & Jones, 1996). Waste in the context of lean production is diverse including overproduction, waiting times, unnecessary movement of materials, inappropriate processing, inventory, defects, underutilization of people, environmental waste and underutilization of facilities. Value added activities include activities perceived as being important by the customer and which are performed correctly the first time (Kollberg et al., 2007; Womack & Jones, 1996).

The literature suggests the need of implementing a bundle of multifaceted practices that work synergistically to minimize waste for the successful implementation of lean production (e.g., Dal Pont, Furlan, & Vinelli, 2008; Flynn, Schroeder, & Flynn, 1999; Karlsson & Åhlström, 1996; Panizzolo, 1998; Shah & Ward, 2003). These multifaceted bundles of lean production practices are also referred to as the determinants of lean production (Karlsson & Åhlström 1996). Table 1 shows a representative view of broadly classified lean production practices. Some past research identified the determinants that are internal to the organization (e.g., James-Moore & Gibbons, 1997; Karlsson & Åhlström, 1996) while some others identified the determinants that are both internal and external to the organization (e.g., Doolen & Hacker, 2005; Shah & Ward, 2007).

Table 1

A term used in conjunction with lean production is *leanness*, which is the relative measure of how lean the system is or the extent of the adoption of lean production practices (Bayou & de Korvin, 2008; Bhasin, 2011; Wan & Chen, 2008). According to Bayou and de Korvin (2008), a firm can achieve different levels of leanness, namely, lean to leaner to the leanest by improving its efficiency, effectiveness or both; the leanest level is the state of perfection. Our review of the literature suggests that the lean production practices shown in Table 1 could be used as the determinants of leanness or the extent of the adoption of lean production. The following sections review, in brief, the literature within the scope of the study to support our research model shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1

Effect of lean production practices on operational performance

Operational performance or manufacturing plant performance is explained in terms of various dimensions such as the manufacturing plant's labour efficiency (Arthur, 1994), machine efficiency (Youndt, Snell, & Lepak, 1996), conformance quality (Cua, McKone, & Schroeder, 2001; Flynn, Sakakibara, & Schroeder, 1995; Swink, Narasimhan, & Wang, 2007), manufacturing plant productivity (Ichniowski, Shaw, & Prennushi, 1997), schedule attainment (Bozarth, Warsing, Flynn, & Flynn, 2009), on-time delivery (Cua et al., 2001; Sakakibara et al., 1997; Swink et al., 2007; Youndt et al., 1996), inventory management (Hofer, Eroglu, & Hofer, 2012; Inman & Mehra, 1993; Youndt et al., 1996), production volume flexibility (Cua et al., 2001; Swink et al., 2007) and manufacturing cost efficiency (Bozarth et al., 2009; Callen, Fader, & Krinsky, 2000; Swink et al., 2007). The dimensions used by previous researchers to explain the operational performance of a manufacturing plant are detailed in Tables 2 and 3. Overall, the achievements in operational performance enhance a firm's manufacturing competitive capabilities (Jabbour et al., 2013; Swink et al., 2007).

The literature on lean production suggests that the simultaneous implementation of a bundle of lean production practices may result in higher levels of achievement in the manufacturing plant performance by streamlining manufacturing processes and increasing process consistency (Birdi et al., 2008; Combs, Liu, Hall, & Ketchen, 2006; Moyano-Fuentes and Sacristán-Díaz, 2012; Patterson, West, & Wall, 2004; Shah & Ward, 2003). Some of these achievements in the manufacturing plant due to the effective implementation of lean production practices are; increase in productivity, improved quality, decrease in cost and reduction in lead times (Birdi et al., 2008; Flynn et al., 1995; Karlsson & Åhlström, 1996; Shah & Ward, 2003).

Table 2 is a result of an extensive review of the literature on empirical studies that investigated the relationship between lean production practices and operational performance at the factory level. Table 2 suggests that the simultaneous adoption of a bundle of practices may increase operational performance – the higher the leanness, the greater will be the positive effects on operational performance (e.g., Callen et al., 2000; Cua et al., 2001; Shah & Ward, 2003; de Menezes et al., 2010). Based on the findings of previous studies reviewed in Table 2, it is hypothesized as:

Hypothesis 1. The adoption of lean production practices results in positive operational performance

Table 2

Effect of operational performance on firm performance

The firm performance or business performance is explained in terms of various dimensions such as firm-level productivity (Cappelli and Newmark, 2001; Fabling and Grimes, 2010; Guthrie, 2001; Huselid, 1995); market performance of business (Fabling and Grimes, 2010; Swink et al., 2007); financial performance of business (Akhtar, Ding, & Ge, 2008; Bhattacharya, Gibson, & Doty, 2005; Hofer et al., 2012; Ngo, Lau, & Foley, 2008), profitability of business (Fabling and Grimes, 2010; Swink et al., 2007) and the ultimate stakeholder satisfaction (Swink et al., 2007). The dimensions used by previous research to explain firm performance are detailed in Tables 2 and 3.

The specific literature on lean production suggests that lean production practices enhance operational performance (as proposed in H1), and in turn enhance firm performance (e.g., Birdi et al., 2008; Hofer et al., 2012). In other words, operational performance mediates the relationship between lean production practices and firm performance. However, it is very rare to find previous empirical studies that investigated the relationship between lean production practices, operational performance and firm performance in a single study. Still, as can be seen in Table 2, Hofer et al. (2012) taking inventory leanness as a measure of operational performance found that inventory leanness mediates lean production practices and financial performance of the business. Sakakibara et al. (1997) taking inventory turnover, on time delivery, cycle time and lead time as the measures of operational performance found that operational performance mediates operational management practices and firm performance. Birdi et al. (2008) supported this mediating relationship showing that lean production practices increase factory-level (operational) performance which in turn increase the profitability and return on assets of the business. Based on the findings of previous studies reviewed in Table 2, it is hypothesized as:

Hypothesis 2. Operational performance mediates the relationship between the adoption of lean production practices and firm performance.

Effects of HRM practices on lean production practices, operational performance and firm performance

The literature offers a number of perspectives on the contribution of HRM to firm performance and its implications for the deployment of organizational resources (e.g., time, finance and people) (Barney, 1991, Chandler, 1962; Purcell, 1989). Chandler (1962) emphasized the importance of structural aspects in specifying the ways in which an organization meets its goals. Purcell (1989) perceived HRM as an integral part of the business strategy process, where the first order of strategy provides long-run direction for the firm whereas the second order of strategy provides internal operating procedures needed to achieve goals. In the HRM context, the third order of strategy provides HRM functional strategies to achieve specific outcomes. Many firms world-wide have introduced lean production as a second order of strategy to enhance firm performance. However, in practice, it is possible to assume that many firms make decisions on the first and second order of strategies independent of the third order conduct for HRM, and without any involvement of HRM practitioners (see Sparrow & Otaye-Ebede, 2014).

Further, resource-based view (RBV) of the firm suggests that the firm specific valuable resources that are rare, inimitable and difficult to substitute confer a competitive advantage (Barney, 1991). Accordingly, an organization's human resources can be identified as a strategic resource in achieving competitive advantage when it adds value to the organization, when it contributes uniquely to the organization's success, when it is difficult to be substituted, and when continual investment in it decreases the likelihood of imitation by competitors (Huselid, 1995). Table 3 is a result of an extensive review of literature on empirical studies that investigated the relationship between HRM practices and firm performance. As can be seen in Table 3, some studies found a significant positive direct relationship between HRM practices and firm performance (e.g. Delery & Doty, 1996; Guthrie, Flood, Liu, & MacCurtain, 2009; Harel & Tzafrir, 1999; Laursen & Foss, 2003). However, several other studies did not provide conclusive evidence for the direct relationship between HRM practices and firm performance (e.g., Cappelli & Newmark, 2001; Som, 2008). As can be seen in Table 3, Katou and Budhwar (2006), Paul and Anantharaman (2003) and Gong, Law, Chang and Xin (2009) provide empirical evidence for the indirect relationship between HRM practices and firm performance. In other words, these studies support the argument that HRM practices do not directly influence firm performance, rather the HRM practices may influence other mediating variables of the organizational context, which may ultimately influence firm performance (Becker & Gerhart, 1996; Edwards & Wright, 2001).

Table 3

Furthermore, the literature on different areas of management (such as HRM, operations management, management in general) suggests the possibilities of perceiving the implementation of HRM practices as an implementation of innovation (e.g., Braunscheidel, Hamister, Suresh, & Star 2011; Gollan, 2005). Klein and Sorra (1996 p. 1055-1056) state that innovation implementation is “the process of gaining targeted employees’ appropriate and committed use of the innovation”. The effectiveness of innovation implementation is “the quality and consistency of targeted organizational members’ use of the adopted innovation” (Klein & Sorra, 1996 p. 1055-1056). Accordingly, the HRM practices should have the capacity to create and regenerate value through the application of appropriate policies and practices to sustain new work systems (Gollan, 2005).

In the above context, by the term HRM practices, our study is confined to practices that contribute to the construction, institutionalisation and maintenance of lean production supporting organizational change processes. For instance, training as an HRM practice can create more competent and reliable behaviour and a greater trust between employees based on the expectation that others will behave in a helpful manner that is reliable and predictable in performing job duties in lean production. This conceptualization of HRM practices would ostensibly include a wide array of practices in the context of advanced manufacturing such as job design (Forrester, 1995; Karlsson & Åhlström, 1996; MacDuffie, 1995; Snell & Dean, 1992), performance evaluation (Ashford & Cumming, 1984), training (Evans & Davis, 2005; Wright & Snell, 1998) and communication and feedback (Losonci et al., 2011). In this regard, the literature suggests that the direct impact of HRM practices on firm performance can be enhanced when a bundle of HRM practices are implemented by taking advantage of synergies between individual practices (Arthur, 1994; Combs et al., 2006; MacDuffie, 1995). It is also argued that different combinations of practices might be available, which are equally effective (Becker & Huselid, 2010). Further, the literature provides evidence that the successful implementation of lean production may be contingent upon the socio-cultural, historical and environmental context of the country under investigation (see James & Jones, 2014; Procter & Radnor, 2014). We empirically investigated HRM practices that are *actually* practiced by the firms that had implemented lean production in Sri Lanka.

Building on the arguments made above, the following paragraphs review the specific literature on the interdependencies between the second order of strategy in terms of internal operating procedures and the third order of HRM functional strategies (as specified by Purcell, 1989) to achieve firm specific outcomes in lean production or in the context of other

advanced manufacturing technologies. In doing so, previous studies reviewed in Table 2 and Table 3 are used to support our arguments.

As can be seen in Table 2 and 3, some previous studies (such as Arthur, 1994; Birdi et al., 2008; Ichniowski et al., 1997; Sakakibara et al. 1997; Youndt et al., 1996) investigated the effect of HRM practices on intermediate and process-related criteria such as operational performance. As can be seen in Table 2, Birdi et al. (2008) concluded that unlike operational management practices, HRM practices are significant in predicting productivity. Furlan, Vinelli and Dal Pont (2011) provide support for the existence of complementarity between the practices of total quality management (TQM) and just-in-time (JIT) practices and the enabling role of HRM on this complementarity. As can be seen in Table 3, MacDuffie (1995) found that HRM practices create a synergistic effect by working as a bundle to improve the productivity and quality of a manufacturing plant. The findings of Ahmad and Schroeder (2003) imply that HRM practices have a significant positive effect on operational performance. Hence, Ahmad and Schroeder (2003) concluded that the most immediate and direct effects of HRM practices in a factory could be on operational performance, which in turn influences firm performance. Therefore, HRM practices can be identified as antecedents to lean production.

As can be seen in Table 3, Paul and Anantharaman (2003) found the indirect effect of HRM practices on financial performance of the business through operational performance. Becker and Gerhart (1996, p. 793) state that HRM practices are linked to performance at both firm and factory-levels but “unless and until researchers are able to elaborate and test more complete structural models – for example, models including key intervening variables – it will be difficult to rule out alternative causal models that explain observed associations between the HRM systems and firm performance”. Based on the literature reviewed *so far* (including Table 2 and 3), we see no reason not to believe that the HRM practices which contribute to the construction, institutionalisation and the maintenance of lean production lead to a greater degree of adoption of lean production practices (i.e., leanness) thus creating positive results at the operational level, and so ultimately enhancing performance at the firm-level. Therefore, it is hypothesized as:

Hypothesis 3. Lean production practices and operational performance mediate the relationship between HRM practices and firm performance.

Lean duration

Womack and Jones (1996) state that lean production can only be achieved through time, and it should not be used as a panacea to solve short-term competitive problems. Powell

(1995) identifies the diffusion of innovation as a function of time. When lean production is identified as an organizational innovation, time becomes a key factor in determining the successful spread of concepts, technical information and actual practices within a social system (Powell, 1995). Lean production system implementations require organizations to adapt to new routines, work methods, behavioural patterns that can make changes to organizational culture (Karlsson & Åhlström, 1996; Wickramasinghe & Wickramasinghe, 2011a, 2011b, 2012). Some previous studies provide evidence that the employees evaluate their lean work experience favourably due to their exposure to multi-skills, team work and opportunities for participation, i.e., their exposure to HRM practices (e.g., Womack & Jones, 1996). The literature also provides evidence that organizations fail to make a sustainable transition to advanced manufacturing systems when changes in the manufacturing function do not accompany complementary changes in HRM practices - human resources are managed in ways inconsistent with the requirements of advanced manufacturing systems (e.g., Thirkell & Ashman, 2014; Snell & Dean, 1992; Sparrow & Otaye-Ebede, 2014).

The management literature also emphasizes the difficulties of creating overnight a work environment suitable for a lean production operation, and highlight that the considerable time is required to receive acceptance from shop-floor employees as well as managers (e.g., Braunscheidel et al., 2011; Karlsson and Åhlström, 1996; Sparrow & Otaye-Ebede, 2014). That is, to build a work environment which is conducive to lean production naturally demands changes to the work organization with modifications to work routines, behavioural patterns and changes to the way work tasks are performed. These changes require some time to receive acceptance from shop-floor employees as well as managers (Karlsson and Åhlström, 1996; Sparrow & Otaye-Ebede, 2014; Wickramasinghe & Wickramasinghe, 2011a, 2011b, 2012). In this regard, the importance of *time* has been identified as a key factor in determining the successful spread of concepts, technical information and actual practices within the social system in lean production (such as Powell, 1995; Womack & Jones, 1996; Wickramasinghe & Wickramasinghe, 2011a). Previous research conducted in the West provides evidence that variations in management practices could be found based on how long the lean production is in operation (Birdi et al., 2008; Callen et al., 2000; Sohal & Egglestone, 1994). In addition, previous studies conducted in Sri Lanka also provide evidence that the extent of adoption of human resource-related practices varies according to the duration of the lean production operation (Wickramasinghe & Wickramasinghe, 2011a). However, our review of the management literature suggest that lean duration has so far not received its due attention in evaluating the HRM practices in a lean production operation.

Overall, it is very rare to find empirical studies on the transition of firms to advanced manufacturing systems, the adoption of HRM practices to facilitate such transitions, and the

importance of time in the adoption of HRM practices to facilitate such transitions. Therefore, it is vital to investigate whether time is an important factor in the adoption of HRM practices to create the necessary conditions for the successful implementation of lean production practices, and thereby yielding positive results at the operational and firm-levels. In this context, we introduce the term *lean duration* to refer to *how long the lean production is in operation*, and it is hypothesized as:

Hypothesis 4. Lean duration moderates the relationship between HRM practices and lean production practices in such a way that the longer the duration, the greater will be the adoption of practices.

Methodology

Population and sample

The literature (e.g., Lui, Lau, & Ngo, 2004) suggests that export-oriented firms are more likely to implement new technologies for their survival and growth in the global marketplace. Therefore, our target population was employees in the export-based manufacturing sector. We used three criteria to select the study population in Sri Lanka, i.e., 1) firms need to be established adhering to the regulations of the Board of Investment of Sri Lanka because such firms are compelled to export at least 90% of their output, 2) lean production system should be in operation in the entire production floor, and it should be the standard process of production for at least one year as discussed in Wickramasinghe and Wickramasinghe (2016), and 3) firms should have employed 100 or more employees (refer to Shah and Ward, 2003). We identified 14 firms that come under 22nd and 23rd classifications of the Standard Industrial Classification fulfilling the above criteria. The classification 22 denotes firms in the business sector of “textile mill products” while 23 denotes firms in the business sector of “apparel and other finished products made from fabrics and similar materials”. One of the authors of this paper together with the contact person from each firm randomly selected employees for the survey. Further, the employees were aware of lean initiatives in their respective firms, were involved in implementing them, and were exposed to changes in the work environment. When distributing questionnaires among employees, we covered at least 10% in each firm, and not more than 5% of employees were selected from the same department/unit. Prior to the distribution of the survey questionnaire, we briefed the respondents about the purpose of the study, and ensured the confidentiality of responses.

When considering the firm characteristics, all the firms were established between 1993 and 2004; these were owned by the locals. These firms had implemented lean production systems between 2005 and 2010. The lean duration was coded as 0 = less than

four years and 1 = more than four years considering the distribution of lean implementation by the firms. Sixty three per cent of the firms had implemented lean production more than four years ago while 37% had implemented it less than four years ago. Lean statistics suggested that the firms reached a good progress in lean production implementation with the mean values of work in progress of 35 days, first time through of 70%, the efficiency of the process of 90%, delivery in full on time of 85%, accepted quality level of 91% and cut ship of 90%. When the number of people employed and average annual turnover are considered as measures of firm size, the total number of employees in the firms were between 300 to 5000 while average annual turnover ranged from 80 to 400 Million US Dollars. The main markets served by the firms are the USA and the EU. Each firm had a separate dedicated unit headed by a senior level manager to handle lean implementation.

When considering the current HRM practices in these firms, Yeung, Warner and Rowley, (2008) suggest that employment practices in developing countries suffer from not having an appropriate structure, institutionalization and impact. However, recent empirical findings from Sri Lanka do not support this claim (refer to Akuratiyagamage, 2006; Mamman, Akuratiyagamage, & Rees, 2006). The findings of Mamman et al. (2006), Akuratiyagamage (2006) and Wickramasinghe (2006), all of which were conducted on this industrial sector found that the HRM systems adopted by the firms had been relatively sophisticated reflecting global best practices. Further, the findings of Akuratiyagamage (2006) and Mamman et al. (2006) imply that there are no significant differences between firms owned by the locals and firms with multinational (MNCs) ownership for the implementation of HRM practices, importance having been given to the HRM function in organizational strategy and the human resource (HR) managers' contribution to organizational strategy. Furthermore, the studies of Akuratiyagamage (2006), Mamman and Akuratiyagamage (2005), Mamman et al., (2006) and Wickramasinghe and Gamage (2011) provide evidence for the institutionalisation of HRM functions and the role of HR practitioners. Akuratiyagamage (2006) found that the majority of firms in the sample had specialised departments to manage human resources. Wickramasinghe and Gamage (2011) revealed that all the firms in the sample had HRM departments with about 3 to 10 people performing the HRM activities. In this regard, Mamman et al. (2006) state "the lack of significant differences between local private firms and MNCs in Sri Lanka imply that globalization is contributing to the diffusion and convergence of management practices. The drivers of globalisation such as non-governmental organizations, efficient communication systems, IT and international and professional institutions might have played some roles in the transfer of management practices and philosophies" (Mamman et al., 2006, p. 2017). Still, we have observed that the role of line managers in the lean implementation is very much greater than that of HR managers. In this regard, the previous studies of Thirkell and Ashman (2014) and Sparrow

and Otaye-Ebede (2014) state that despite the importance of HRM issues in lean production, the HRM function was not involved in the lean implementation.

Measures

The measures used for the HRM practices, lean production practices, operational performance, firm performance and lean duration are presented below. All item measures are listed in Appendix 1.

HRM practices

The HRM literature emphasises the need for distinguishing intended HRM practices from the implemented practices (such as Khilji and Wang, 2006). We used three mechanisms to identify the HRM practices that contributed to the institutionalisation of lean production. First, we used prior theoretical and empirical work (refer to Table 2 and 3) to identify the HRM practices that contribute to the institutionalisation of new production systems. Second, we did a preliminary investigation on the study population (= sample) to identify the most implemented HRM practices that facilitated the institutionalisation of lean production. Third, we used prior theoretical and empirical work to isolate any practices that were not prominent in the literature and not identified as highly implemented by the firms, but appeared to fit into our study. Based on the above procedure, a scale of 25 items in a Likert-scale (1 = strongly disagree, 5 = strongly agree, refer to Appendix 1) was developed to obtain the extent of implementation on the production floor. To ensure content and face validity, these items were, first, assessed by a panel of academics and practitioners and second, pre-tested with a sample of appropriate employees.

Lean production practices

The literature on operations management emphasises the need for distinguishing intended practices from implemented practices (e.g., Shah and Ward, 2007). Accordingly, we followed the same procedure mentioned above to identify the lean production practices *that had been implemented* in the production floor. Ultimately, a scale of 38 items in a Likert-scale (1 = strongly disagree, 5 = strongly agree, refer to Appendix 1) was developed to obtain the extent of implementation in the production floor. We used the same procedure mentioned above to ensure content and face validity.

Operational performance

Following Youndt et al. (1996), we relied on the subjective measures of operational performance because of the difficulties in securing secondary data from all the firms.

Previous studies showed that the subjective measures of firm performance correlate well with the objective measures of firm performance (Guest, Michie, Conway and Sheehan 2003); the bias associated with self-reported firm performance data is limited (Wall et al., 2004). Based on our preliminary investigation mentioned above, a scale of seven items in a Likert-scale (1 = strongly disagree, 5 = strongly agree, refer to Appendix 1) was developed to capture the operational performance. We used the same procedure mentioned above to ensure content and face validity.

Firm performance

We relied on the subjective measures of firm performance as reasoned above. After an extensive review of literature, we used the four-item scale of Khandwalla (1977) to capture the firm performance (1 = strongly disagree, 5 = strongly agree, refer to Appendix 1). This scale has been used widely in studies such as Bae et al. (2003). We used the same procedure mentioned above to ensure content and face validity.

Lean duration

Lean duration refers to the duration of lean production in operation. This was measured in years.

Methods of data analysis

Variables were mean centred before computing the product term, although not mathematically required, so as to produce regression coefficients for the variables that would be interpretable within their actual range of values in the data (Hayes, 2013). We used Harman's single-factor test in SPSS to test common method variance (refer to Podsakoff, MacKenzie, Lee, and Podsakoff, 2003). We further used the common latent factor test in AMOS to confirm this result, which yielded a similar result suggesting that common method variance is not a concern in our data, and thus is unlikely to confound the interpretations of results.

Exploratory factor analysis (EFA) and confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) were performed on the variables. We tested EFA using SPSS for appropriate convergent validity, construct reliability (CR), discriminant validity, internal consistency reliability and factor structure; average variance extracted (AVE) was used to measure convergent validity while the square root of AVE was used to measure discriminant validity (refer to Hair, Black, Babin, Anderson, & Tatham, 2006). As can be seen from Appendices 1 to 5, fit indices of the HRM practices, lean production practices, operational performance and firm performance revealed good fit.

To confirm the factor structures yielded for HRM practices, lean production practices, operational performance and firm performance from SPSS, we conducted CFA using AMOS following Anderson and Gerbing's (1988) recommendation. Accordingly, we assessed CFA results based on chi-square and fit indices. With regard to chi-square, Arbuckle (2007, p. 589-592) shows the importance of interpreting results based on normed chi-square statistic (χ^2/df) instead of interpreting results based on two separate values of chi-square (χ^2) and degrees of freedom (df). It is recommended to have χ^2/df value between 5 and 2 (Arbuckle, 2007; Marsh & Hocevar, 1985; Wheaton, Muthén, Alwin, & Summers, 1977). With regard to fit indices, comparative fit index (CFI), Tucker-Lewis index (TLI) and root mean square error of approximation (RMSEA) were used. Regarding fit indices, CFI and TLI close to 1 but should be above 0.95 (Byrne, 2001; Hu & Bentler, 1999), and RMSEA 0.08 or less (Arbuckle, 2007) are considered as reasonable. We conducted a series of CFA for the 25-item HRM practices scale and indices yielded for χ^2/df statistic and CFI, TLI and RMSEA confirmed that the factors yielded from SPSS as the best fitting (refer to Table 4). In a similar vein, we conducted a series of CFA for the 38-item lean production practices scale and fit indices yielded confirmed that the factors yielded from SPSS as the best fitting (refer to Table 4). With regard to operational performance and firm performance, χ^2/df statistics and fit indices confirmed that treating each measure as single factor constructs provide the best fit for our study, confirming the results of SPSS (refer to Table 4). Wilks' Lambda statistic was obtained to evaluate differences in the 14 firms by lean duration. This analysis revealed non-existent of significant differences ($p > 0.05$) across the firms. We used the PROCESS programme developed by Hayes (2013) to reconfirm the results obtained from CFA. Indirect effects were assessed based on 5,000 bootstrapped samples using bias-corrected 95% confidence intervals (CI) for the size and significance of the effects.

Results and discussion

Appendix 2 shows the results of EFA on the HRM practices. Factor analysis yielded five HRM practices, namely, work design, knowledge sharing, job-related training, supervision and talent management. This supports the multi-dimensional and integrated nature of a bundle of HRM practices that contribute to the institutionalisation of lean production. Appendix 3 shows the results of EFA on lean production practices. Factor analysis yielded seven lean production practices, namely, waste minimization, defects minimization, continuous improvement, JIT and Pull, cross functional teams, information availability and employee involvement. This supports the multi-dimensional and integrated nature of a bundle of lean production practices that determine how lean a manufacturing system is. As

can be seen in Appendix 4 and 5, the scale items of operational performance and firm performance respectively converged into single components.

Table 4 shows CFA results on best fitting models yielded for the HRM practices, lean production practices, operational performance and firm performance using AMOS following Anderson and Gerbing's (1988) recommendation. As detailed in *Methods of data analysis*, results shown in Table 4 confirmed that the factors yielded from SPSS (in Appendices 2 to 5) as the best fitting. In other words, the 5-factors yielded for HRM practices in EFA using SPSS (shown in Appendix 2) provided the best fit model with $\chi^2/df = 3.821$, CFI = .973, TLI = .944 and RMSEA = .023 in CFA using AMOS. Hence, the fit indices support the distinctiveness of work design, knowledge sharing, job-related training, supervision and talent management as the HRM practices. The 7-factors yielded for lean production practices in EFA using SPSS (shown in Appendix 3) provided the best fit model with $\chi^2/df = 3.373$, CFI = .966, TLI = .930 and RMSEA = .012 in CFA using AMOS. Accordingly, the fit indices support the distinctiveness of waste minimization, defects minimization, continuous improvement, JIT and Pull, cross functional teams, information availability and employee involvement as lean production practices. As can be seen in Table 4, fit indices confirmed treating operational performance and firm performance as single factor constructs confirming results shown in Appendix 4 and 5.

Table 4

Table 5 provides descriptive statistics and inter-correlations for the measures in this study. As can be seen, and as expected, correlations between the variables were statistically significant and in the expected directions.

Table 5

We conducted a series of CFA to examine the relationships predicted in H1, H2, and H3 based on χ^2/df statistic and fit indices of CFI, TLI and RMSEA. The results are shown in Table 6. All the models satisfy the model fit criteria of χ^2/df between 5 and 2 (Marsh & Hocevar, 1985; Wheaton et al., 1977), CFI and TLI close to 1 but above 0.08 (Byrne, 2001; Hu & Bentler, 1999), and RMSEA 0.08 or less (Arbuckle, 2007). Accordingly, lean production

practices significantly positively predict operational performance ($\chi^2/df = 2.789$, CFI = .973, TLI = .959 and RMSEA = .065). This supports H1. Further, results reveal that operational performance mediates the relationship between lean production practices and firm performance ($\chi^2/df = 3.007$, CFI = .941, TLI = .927 and RMSEA = .068). This supports H2. Furthermore, results reveal that lean production practices and operational performance mediate the relationship between the HRM practices and firm performance ($\chi^2/df = 3.204$, CFI = .924, TLI = .905 and RMSEA = .059). This supports H3. Overall, the model comparisons shown in Table 6 led to identify the mediation relationship predicted in H3 as yielding a better fit to the data when compared to alternative models tested.

Table 6

Although we have already shown the support for lean production practices and operational performance in the relationship between HRM practices and firm performance using the structural equation modelling approach (refer Table 6), we nevertheless used the PROCESS programme (Hayes, 2013) to confirm this result. We performed the analysis based on 5,000 bootstrapped samples using bias-corrected 95% CI for the size and significance of the effects. Table 7 presents the results from this analysis. The indirect effect was significant at the 95% level of significance ($B = .152$, $p < .001$) as indicated when the lower (LL 95% CI) and upper (UL 95% CI) levels of the confidence intervals did not include zero. That is, lean production practices and operational performance mediated the effect of HRM practices on firm performance, and in the expected direction. Figure 2 illustrates the statistical diagram of the mediation model tested in the study with path coefficients from PROCESS. Results shown in Table 7 (from PROCESS) confirms results shown in Table 6 (from AMOS) that the indirect effect of HRM practices on firm performance (through lean production practices and operational performance) was positive and significant, consistent with H3. With regard to H4, we conducted a series of CFA to confirm the effect of lean duration based on χ^2/df statistic and fit indices of CFI, TLI and RMSEA. The model comparisons shown in Table 8 led to identify that the hypothesised model ($\chi^2/df = 4.431$, CFI = .901, TLI = .855 and RMSEA = .054) yielded a better fit to the data when compared to alternative models tested. This supports H4. Figure 3 illustrates the interaction of HRM practices and lean duration on the adoption of lean production practices. We followed the guidelines of Aiken and West (1991) to conduct simple effects test for the slopes of the lines.

The results revealed that the relationship between the HRM practices and lean production practices is moderated for high ($t = 5.354, p < 0.001$), medium ($t = 3.842, p < 0.001$) and low ($t = 3.595, p < 0.001$) levels of lean duration. Figure 4 was created to depict AMOS estimates for hypothesised model. Accordingly, the HRM practices influences the adoption of lean production practices in such a way that the longer the duration, the greater will be the adoption.

Table 7

Figure 2

Table 8

Figure 3

Figure 4

Conclusions and implications

Based on the conceptual model developed for the study, we concurrently analysed the structural relationships between HRM practices, lean production practices, lean duration, operational performance and firm performance. The results of the analyses supported all the hypotheses set for the study. Since it is very rare to find prior empirical studies that have integrated all these variables in the current study context, we believe that the findings of our study make a unique contribution to theory and practice.

With regard to the theoretical contribution of the study, first, we developed a model to explain the contribution of HRM practices in the implementation of lean production, and in turn on operational and firm performance. The model we developed was in line with the arguments made in the literature (such as Barney, 1991, Chandler, 1962; Purcell, 1989). Based on the strategic human resource management (SHRM) perspective that builds on the RBV (Barney, 1991), we conceptualised the HRM practices as practices that contribute to the construction, institutionalisation and maintenance of lean production supporting

organizational change processes. We empirically investigated already implemented HRM practices in contrast to intended practices that lead to the institutionalization of lean production, reflecting the operational landscape. We developed operational measures for the HRM practices that contribute to the institutionalization of lean production, which were not operationalized in prior studies as we did in our study. By doing so, we tried to identify most of the salient dimensions that lead to institutionalize lean production. We empirically identified a bundle of multifaceted HRM practices that contribute to the institutionalization of lean production, namely work design, job-related training, talent management, supervision and knowledge sharing. The practices we identified are in line with the literature that emphasises the importance of HRM practices for achieving superior and sustainable performance through lean production regardless of the industrial sector where it is pursued (such as Marodin & Saurin, 2013; Parast, 2013; Shah & Ward, 2003). Further, our results also support the findings of previous empirical studies on the importance of implementing a bundle of HRM practices for increased firm performance (such as Arthur, 1994; Becker & Huselid, 2010; Combs et al., 2006; MacDuffie, 1995) and for the successful adoption of flexible production systems (such as Birdi et al., 2008; de Menezes et al., 2010; Ichniowski et al. 1997; MacDuffie 1995; Patterson et al., 2004).

In a similar vein, second, we empirically investigated a bundle of lean production practices. Building on previous research such as Birdi et al. (2008), Flynn et al. (1995) and Furlan et al. (2011), we identified diverse and inter-related lean production practices. In doing so, we empirically investigated already implemented lean production practices in contrast to intended practices. Therefore, our operational measures of lean production practices reflect the operational landscape of the firm. Further, we empirically showed the positive and significant relationship between the HRM practices and lean production practices. Therefore, our findings support Marodin and Saurin (2013) and Parast (2013) that the HRM practices are important determinants in implementing lean production practices. Furthermore, we provided evidence for a significant positive relationship between lean production practices and operational performance. Therefore, our findings support the findings of Callen et al. (2000), Cua et al., (2001), Shah and Ward (2003), and de Menezes et al. (2010), who provided evidence for this significant positive relationship in the Western context.

Third, we integrated a bundle of HRM practices, a bundle of lean production practices and operational performance in a single study, and investigated the mediating relationship. As can be seen from Table 2, three previous studies (namely, Birdi et al., 2008; de Menezes et al., 2010; Patterson et al., 2004) integrated a bundle of HRM practices and a bundle of lean production practices with operational performance, and these three studies provide empirical evidence from the Western context. However, except Patterson et al.

(2004), the other two studies investigated the direct relationship. Therefore, our results on the mediating relationship between the HRM practices, lean production practices and operational performance make unique contribution to the literature, and also in a non-Western context. As such, the findings will be a source of general guidance in stimulating future research in this area.

Fourth, the findings revealed the importance of the duration of lean production in operation in achieving success in manufacturing processes that had implemented lean production. Our findings showed that the positive effects of HRM practices on lean production practices, and in turn on operational performance and firm performance are conditioned by the duration of lean production in operation. Hence, our empirical findings support Womack and Jones (1996) and Powell (1995) that the adoption of lean production can only be achieved through time. Hence, based on the findings, we could conclude that if a firm exploited (developed, instituted and implemented) the HRM practices to their highest potential, over time it may be able to create a lean production system that yields the highest performance through incremental improvement. This implies that early implementers may have more advantages over followers. We identify this as one of the unique contributions of our study since our extensive review of the literature revealed the difficulty of finding experiences consequent to the introduction of new manufacturing systems in emerging or developing countries. Changes occurring with the globalisation of business operations and increase in operating costs in the West have increased the importance of developing countries in the manufacturing and export trade. Therefore, the findings from a study in the context of an Asian developing country are interesting, relevant and timely.

Fifth, the study conceptualized and tested a structural model that links HRM practices to firm performance through factory-level mediators - an area which still remains less understood and less apprehended. The relationships found in the study are the result of our attempt to take into account not only the two ends of HRM practices and firm performance but also the relationships in between. This is in line with the call for more research including intervening variables to explain associations between HRM and firm performance to a better understanding of how HRM can be used to enhance firm performance (Arthur 1994; Combs et al. 2006; Becker and Gerhart, 1996). In this context, we have made a contribution to the literature on SHRM by incorporating relationships that the HRM practices have with lean implementation at the manufacturing plant, thus providing a better understanding of the interplay between HRM practices, lean production practices, lean duration, operational performance and firm performance. Our results support the indirect relationship between HRM practices and firm performance through lean production practices and operational performance, in such a way that the longer the duration of lean production in operation, the greater will be the adoption of lean production practices. Accordingly, a firm may develop

and simultaneously implement a set of HRM practices by exposing employees to diverse experiences over time so that they would be capable of using these under different demand conditions, which are not easily imitable. In other words, the lean duration creates a situation where bundles of practices are difficult to be imitated since imitation demands an understanding of precise mechanisms by which each element interacts with another. Therefore, the overall result of our study supports the argument made by Becker and Gerhart (1996) and Edwards and Wright (2001) that HRM practices influence firm performance through other mediating and moderating variables of the organizational context, which may ultimately influence firm performance. Overall, the conceptualization and testing of our structural model help to better understand the contribution of HRM practices to firm performance and their implications for the deployment of organizational resources as emphasized by Barney (1991), Chandler (1962) and Purcell (1989).

With regard to the specific contribution of our study for practice, first, the findings imply that the success of lean production is largely influenced by the way in which HRM practices are designed, developed and implemented to deliver organizational excellence. For instance, when numerical flexibility becomes inappropriate due to quality requirements, customisation, continuous innovation and product differentiation, firms have to rely on job-related training to create flexibility in terms of employee skills and behaviours. We have identified job-related training and workforce optimisation as important HRM practices leading to the institutionalisation of lean production. Job-related training may lead to skill flexibility by providing potential alternative uses to which the individuals' skills could be applied and how individuals with different skills could be deployed. Job-related training may also lead to behavioural flexibility, where the individuals' behaviour could become adapted to the demands of different work situations while maintaining the similarity of responses by different individuals to similarly perceived situations.

Second, our study was on the HRM practices adopted by export-based firms to facilitate the implementation of lean production. On the one hand, when firms are faced with similar environmental conditions (i.e., political, legal, economic, social and also export market) they may orient themselves towards mimicking best practices that other firms had adopted (Lui et al. 2004). On the other hand, the RBV argues that a firm could enjoy competitive advantage by adopting distinctive practices which are the basis of inimitability (Barney & Wright, 1998). Then the question arises, how could firms compete more effectively by adopting similar sets of HRM and lean production practices in view of rapid globalisation? Here, the duration of lean implementation becomes critical. A firm could develop practice flexibility (of HRM practices as well as lean production practices) over time to respond quickly to a variety of environmental changes by re-synthesising, re-configuring, and re-deploying its practices. Therefore, the lean duration creates a situation where a

bundle of HRM practices is much more difficult to be imitated when compared with individual practices since imitation demands an understanding of the precise mechanisms by which each element interacts with another.

Third, although investigating the role of the HRM function in the implementation of lean production was not our specific intention in the study, we observed during our data collection that line managers in the production function play a key role in the construction, institutionalization and maintenance of not only operations management practices but also the HRM practices. The absence of HR professionals in the lean implementation could create issues in managing people and in consequence, the sustainability of lean production (see Sparrow & Otaye-Ebede, 2014). Hence, our observations support the situations identified by Sparrow and Otaye-Ebede (2014) and Thirkell and Ashman (2014). This emphasises the need for identifying conditions in the organizational context that challenge and exclude the HRM function from lean implementation.

Limitations and future research

Our study was designed based on cross-sectional data. Still, we were able to gain access to and collect first-hand primary survey data rather than relying on secondary data sources. Future research designed based on longitudinal studies may provide a deeper understanding. We assessed the practices already implemented in the firms to isolate practices that had failed to be implemented as well as practices that had been implemented badly. Future research could also incorporate appropriate internal and external variables into the equation, such as resource availability to invest in new technologies. Further, it is possible to argue that a higher level of firm performance may strengthen the implementation of lean production, which may in turn enhance firm performance. However, in the real world, such occurrences of endogeneity are possible for many organizational practices. Future research could test for such endogeneity. Finally, our study was confined to the manufacturing function of a firm. Future research could incorporate backward and forward functions of the value chain that are linked with HRM practices, lean production and firm performance to gain deeper understanding.

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Figures

Figure 1. Conceptual model

Figure 2. Statistical diagram of mediation with unstandardized path coefficients

*** $p < .001$ (two-tailed)

Figure 3. Moderating effect at high and low levels of lean duration

Figure 4. Statistical diagram with standardized path coefficients

*** $p < .001$ (two-tailed)

Tables

Table 1 Commonly cited determinants of lean production

Study	Practices included	Method used to derive practices
James-Moore and Gibbons (1997)	Waste elimination, flexibility, people utilization, process control, and optimization	Scoring method
Panizzolo (1998)	Process and equipment, manufacturing planning and control, human resources, product design, supplier relationships, and customer relationships	Principle component factor analysis
Flynn et al. (1999)*	Employee development, management technical competence, design for customer needs, worker participation, proprietary equipment, continuous improvement, process control, feedback of information, pull system, and JIT supplier relationship	Cronbach's alpha and inter-item correlation
Karlsson and Åhlström (1996)	Elimination of waste, continuous improvement, zero defects, JIT deliveries, pull of materials, multifunctional teams, decentralisation, integration of functions, and vertical information systems	Clinical research project
Shah and Ward (2003)	JIT, TQM, TPM, and HRM	Principle component factor analysis
Doolen and Hacker (2005)	Manufacturing equipment and processes, shop-floor management, new product development, supplier management, customer relationships, and workforce management	Conceptual
Shah and Ward (2007)	Supplier feedback, JIT delivery by suppliers, customer involvement, pull, continuous flow, set-up time reduction, TPM, statistical process control, and employee involvement	Principle component factor analysis and confirmatory factor analysis
Dal Pont et al. (2008)	JIT, TQM, and HRM	Confirmatory factor analysis
Furlan et al. (2011)	JIT and TQM	Confirmatory factor analysis

Note: The table was created by the authors. * practices for competitive performance

Table 2 Effects of lean production practices on performance

Study	Unit of analysis: firm level/facility level	Independent variables (IVs)		Dependent variables (DVs)		If IVs and DVs were perceived, did same respondent respond to both?	Research design	Nature of the relationship tested between IVs and DVs ***	Relationship between main IVs and DVs
		Main IV “lean production practices/operations management practices” (number of constructs/nature of measures)	Other IVs included *** (number of constructs /nature of measures)	Operational/Plant level performance (number of constructs/nature of measures)	Other DVs included*** (number of constructs/nature of measures)				
Inman and Mehra (1993)	Manufacturing plant	Inventory and utilization (Two constructs/perceived; each construct has multiple items)	No	Operational performance (One construct/not specified: construct has multiple items)	No	Not specified	Cross-sectional, statistical	Direct	Significant, positive
Flynn et al. (1995)	Manufacturing plant	“JIT practices” comprise of kanban, lot size reduction, set-up time reduction, and JIT scheduling. “TQM practices” comprise of statistical process control, product design, and customer focus (Two constructs with sub-constructs for each/perceived; each sub-construct has multiple items)	“Infrastructure practices” comprised of information feedback, plant environment, management support, supplier relationship, and workforce management (One construct with five sub-constructs /perceived; each sub-construct has multiple items)	“Quality performance” (perceived; construct has multiple items) and “JIT performance” (objective) (Two constructs, one perceived and the other objective)	No	No	Cross-sectional, statistical	Indirect	Significant, positive
Sakakibara et al. (1997)	Manufacturing plant	Set-up time reduction, schedule flexibility, maintenance, equipment layout, Kanban, and JIT supplier relationship (Six constructs/perceived; each construct has multiple items)	“Infrastructure practices” comprised of product design, workforce management, organizational characteristics, quality management, and manufacturing strategy (One construct with five sub-constructs /perceived; each sub-construct has multiple items)	Inventory turnover, on time delivery, cycle time, and lead time (Four constructs/objective)	Unit cost of manufacturing, quality of product/service, fast delivery, flexibility to change volume, and comparison with competition on a global basis (Five constructs/perceived; each contain single item)	N/A	Cross-sectional, statistical	Indirect	Non- significant. Suggested the importance of “other IVs” of workforce management.
Callen et al.	Manufacturing	JIT-TQM	No	Productivity in inventory	No	N/A	Cross-	Direct	Significant, positive

(2000)	plant	(One construct/perceived; construct has multiple items)		usage, quality of processes, total and variable costs, and operating profits, (Four constructs/objective)			sectional, statistical		
Cua et al. (2001)	Manufacturing plant	TQM, JIT, and TPM (Three constructs/perceived; each construct has multiple items)	HR and strategic oriented common practices (One construct with several sub constructs/perceived; each sub-construct has multiple items)	Cost efficiency, conform quality, on-time delivery, and volume flexibility (Four constructs/perceived: each contain single item)	No	No	Cross-sectional, statistical	Direct	Significant, positive
Shah and Ward (2003)	Manufacturing plant	JIT, TQM, HRM and TPM (Four constructs/perceived; each construct has multiple items)	No	Operational performance (One construct/perceived; construct has multiple items)	No	Yes	Cross-sectional, statistical	Direct	Significant, positive
Patterson et al. (2004)	Firm	AMT, TQM, and JIT (Three constructs/perceived; each construct has multiple items)	Job enrichment and skill enhancement (Two constructs/perceived; each construct has multiple items)	None	Company labour productivity, and Profit (Two constructs/objective)	No	Cross-sectional, statistical	Indirect	Significant, positive
Birdi et al. (2008)±	Firm	TQM, JIT, AMT, and supply chain partnering (Four constructs/coded based on usage – “no use/any use”)	Empowerment, extensive training, and team-based working (Three constructs/coded based on usage – “no use/any use”)	None	Company productivity (One construct/developed by authors: objective)	N/A	Longitudinal, statistical	Direct	Non- significant. The main IVs of TQM, JIT, AMT, and supply chain partnering did not show significant relationship. However, “other IVs” of empowerment, training, and teamwork showed significant positive effect on productivity.

de Menezes et al. (2010) ±	Firm	Integrated computer-based technology, JIT, Supply chain partnering, TQM (Four constructs/coded based on usage – “no use/any use”)	Empowerment, learning culture, team-based work (Three constructs/coded based on usage – “no use/any use”)	None	Company productivity (One construct/developed by authors: objective)	N/A	Longitudinal, statistical	Direct	Significant, positive
Furlan et al. (2011)	Manufacturing plant	JIT and TQM (Two constructs/perceived; each construct has multiple items)	HRM (One construct/perceived; construct has multiple items)	Operational performance (One construct/perceived; construct has multiple items)	No	Yes	Cross-sectional, statistical	Indirect	Significant, positive
Jabbour et al. (2013)	Manufacturing plant	Lean practices (One construct/perceived; construct has multiple items)	HRM practices (One construct/perceived; construct has multiple items)	Operational performance (One construct/perceived; construct has multiple items)	No	Yes	Cross-sectional, statistical	Indirect	Significant, positive
Hofer et al. (2012)	Firm	“external lean practices” comprise of supplier feedback, supplier JIT, supplier development and customer involvement, and “internal lean practices” comprise of pull manufacturing, continuous flow manufacturing, set-up time reduction, statistical process control, employee involvement and TPM (Two constructs with sub-constructs for each /perceived; each sub-construct has multiple items)	No	Inventory leanness (One construct/Indicator developed by authors: objective)	Financial performance (One construct/objective)	N/A	Cross-sectional, statistical	Indirect	Significant, positive

Note: The table was created by the authors. *** Other variables that come within the scope of the current study were included. Controls were not included as IVs but mediators and moderators were included. ± Used the same data set.

Table 3 Effects of HRM practices on performance

Study	Unit of analysis: firm level/facility level	Independent variables (IVs)		Dependent variable (DVs): Performance (number of constructs/nature of measures)	If IVs and DVs were perceived, did same respondent respond to both?	Research design	Nature of the relationship tested between IVs and DVs ***	Relationship between IVs and DVs
		Main IV "HRM practices" (number of constructs/nature of measures)	Other IVs included *** (number of constructs /nature of measures)					
Arthur (1994)	Manufacturing plant	Commitment HR system and control HR system (Two constructs/perceived; each construct has multiple items)	No	Mill's labour efficiency, scrap rate, and Mill's Labour turnover (Three constructs/objective)	N/A	Cross-sectional, statistical	Direct	Significant, positive
Huselid (1995)	Firm	Employee skills and organizational structures, and employee motivation (Two constructs/perceived; each construct has multiple items)	Internal fit and external fit (Two constructs/perceived and calculated by authors)	Firm level productivity, corporate financial performance, and employee turnover (Three constructs/objective)	No	Cross-sectional, statistical	Indirect	Significant, positive
MacDuffie (1995)	Manufacturing plant	"Production organization index" comprise of use of buffers index, work systems index, and HRM policies index (One construct/developed by authors: each index has multiple items)		Labour productivity and quality (Two constructs/objective)	N/A	Cross-sectional, statistical	Direct	Significant, positive
Delery and Doty (1996)	Firm	Use of internal career ladders, formal training systems, results-oriented appraisal, performance-based compensation, employment security, employee voice, and broadly defined jobs (Seven constructs/perceived; each construct has multiple items)	Organization's strategy (One construct/perceived; construct has multiple items)	Financial performance (Two constructs/objective)	N/A	Cross-sectional, statistical	Direct and Indirect	Significant, positive
Youndt et al. (1996)	Manufacturing plant	Staffing, training, performance appraisal, and compensation. (Four constructs/perceived; each construct has multiple items)	"Manufacturing strategy" comprise of quality, delivery flexibility, scope flexibility, and cost (One construct with	Machine efficiency, customer alignment, and employee productivity at manufacturing facility level (Three constructs/perceived; each construct	Yes	Cross-sectional, statistical	Indirect	Significant, positive

			four sub-constructs /perceived; each sub-construct has multiple items)	has multiple items)				
Ichniowski et al. (1997)	Manufacturing plant	Incentive pay, recruiting and selection, team work, employment security, flexible job assignment, skills training, communication, and labour relations (Seven constructs/coded into dummy variables by authors)	HRM systems (Four constructs /developed by authors)	Manufacturing plant productivity (One construct/developed by authors: objective)	No	Longitudinal, statistical	Direct	Significant, positive
Harel and Tzafrir (1999)	Firm	Recruitment, selection, internal labor market, training, participation, compensation, and grievance procedure (Seven constructs/perceived; each construct has multiple items)	No	Firm performance and market performance (Two constructs/perceived; each construct has multiple items)	Yes	Cross-sectional, statistical	Direct	Significant, positive
Cappelli and Newmark (2001)	Firm	Formal TQM programme, self-managed teams, regularly scheduled meetings to discuss work-related problems, team work training, job rotation, cross training, pay for skill programmes, and gain/profit sharing (Eight constructs/perceived; each construct has multiple items)	Benchmarking (One construct/perceived; construct has multiple items)	Firm productivity, total labor costs per worker, and labour efficiency at firm level (Three constructs/objective)	N/A	Longitudinal, statistical	Direct	Significant, positive
Guthrie (2001)	Firm	HRM practices (One construct/perceived; construct has multiple items)	Employee retention rate (One construct/inverse of labour turnover rate: calculated by the author)	Firm productivity (One construct/objective)	Yes	Cross-sectional, statistical	Indirect	Significant, positive
Ahmad and Schroeder (2003)	Manufacturing plant	Employment security, selective hiring, use of self-managed teams and decentralization, use of compensation contingent on organizational performance, the extent of training, reduced status distinctions, and sharing	No	Operational performance (One construct/perceived; construct has multiple items)	N/A	Cross-sectional, statistical	Direct	Significant, positive

		of information. (Seven constructs/perceived; each construct has multiple items)						
Bae et al. (2003)	Firm	HR flow, work system, reward system, and employee upward influence (Four constructs/perceived; each construct has multiple items)	No	Financial performance (One construct/perceived; construct has multiple items)	Yes	Cross-sectional, statistical	Direct	Significant, positive
Guest et al. (2003)	Firm	Recruitment and selection, training and development, appraisal, financial flexibility, job design, two-way communication, employment security and the internal labour market, single status and harmonization, and quality (Nine constructs/perceived; each construct has multiple items)	No	Labour productivity and financial performance (Two constructs with single items/ perceived) Labour productivity and financial performance (Three constructs/objective) (Total of five constructs, two perceived and three objective)	N/A	cross-sectional and longitudinal data	Direct	Significant, positive
Laursen and Foss (2003)	Firm	Interdisciplinary workgroups, quality circles, systems for collecting employee proposals, planned job rotation, delegation of decision rights, integration of functions, performance related pay, firm internal training, and firm external training (Nine constructs/perceived; each construct has multiple items)	No	Innovation performance (One construct/perceived; construct has multiple items)	Not specified	Cross-sectional, statistical	Direct	Significant, positive
Paul Anantharaman and (2003)	Firm	Selection, induction, training, job design, work environment, performance appraisal, compensation, career development, and incentives (Nine constructs/perceived; each construct has multiple items)	Competence, teamwork, organizational commitment and customer orientation (Four constructs/perceived; each construct has multiple items)	“Operational performance” comprise of employee retention, employee productivity, product quality, speed of delivery, and operating cost (Five constructs each with single item/perceived) “Financial performance” (One construct with	No	Cross-sectional, statistical	Indirect	Significant, positive

				multiple items/perceived)				
Lui et al. (2004)	Firm	Employee development, career development, performance-based compensation, selective hiring, and strategic HR planning (Five constructs/perceived; each construct has multiple items)	Mimetic HR and strategic HR orientation (Two constructs/perceived; each construct has multiple items)	Firm performance (One construct/perceived; construct has multiple items)	Yes	Cross-sectional, statistical	Direct	Significant, positive
Bhattacharya et al. (2005)	Firm	Skill flexibility, behavior flexibility, and HR practice flexibility (Three constructs/perceived; each construct has multiple items)	No	Financial performance (One construct/ objective)	Yes	Cross-sectional, statistical	Direct	Significant, positive
Katou and Budhwar (2006)	Firm	Resourcing and development, and reward and relations (Two constructs/perceived; each construct has multiple items)	“HRM outcomes” comprise of skills, attitudes, and behaviour (One construct with three sub-constructs/perceived; each sub-construct has multiple items)	Firm performance (One construct/perceived; construct has multiple items)	Yes	Cross-sectional, statistical	Indirect	Significant, positive
Akhtar et al. (2008)	Firm	Training, participation, employment security, job description, results-oriented appraisal, internal career opportunities, and profit sharing (Seven constructs/perceived; except profit sharing all other constructs have multiple items)	No	Product/service performance and financial performance (Two constructs/perceived; each construct has multiple items)	N/A	Cross-sectional, statistical	Direct	Significant, positive
Ngo et al. (2008)	Firm	HRM practices (One construct/perceived; construct has multiple items)	No	Financial performance and operational performance (Two constructs with single items /perceived)	yes	Cross-sectional, statistical	Direct	Significant, positive
Som (2008)	Firm	Role of HRM department, recruitment, re-training and re-deployment, performance appraisal and compensation,	No	Firm performance (One construct/perceived; construct has multiple	No	Cross-sectional, statistical	Direct	Significant, positive

		and reward practices (Five constructs/perceived; each construct has multiple items)		items)				
Gong et al. (2009)	Firm	Employment security, reduction of status distinction, selective hiring, participation in decision making through teams, comparatively high pay contingent on performance, extensive training, career planning and advancement, and performance appraisal (Eight constructs/perceived; each construct has multiple items)	Commitment (One construct/perceived; construct has multiple items)	Firm performance (One construct/perceived; construct has multiple items)	No	Cross-sectional, statistical	Indirect	Significant, positive
Guthrie et al. (2009)	Firm	HRM practices (One construct/perceived; construct has multiple items)	No	Absenteeism, employee turnover, labour productivity, and labour expense. (Four constructs/objective)	No	Cross-sectional, statistical	Direct	Significant, positive
Subramony (2009)	Firm	Empowerment, motivation, and skill-enhancement (Three constructs/perceived; each construct has multiple items)	No	Firm performance (One construct/composite score developed by the author: objective)	N/A	Meta-analysis	Direct	Significant, positive
Fabling and Grimes (2010)	Firm	Employee satisfaction, performance pay, employee training (Three constructs/coded into a binary scale by authors)	No	Profitability, firm productivity, market share (Three constructs/perceived: coded into a binary scale by the authors)	Not specified	Cross-sectional, statistical	Direct	Significant, positive

Note: The table was created by the authors. *** Other variables that come within the scope of the current study were included. Controls were not included as IVs but mediators and moderators were included.

Table 4. CFA results for measures of HRM practices, lean production practices, operational performance and firm performance

Measure	χ^2/df	CFI	TLI	RMSEA
5-factor HRM practices	3.821	.973	.944	.023
7-factor lean production practices	3.373	.966	.930	.012
1-factor operational performance	3.855	.974	.864	.037
1-factor firm performance	4.356	.962	.808	.052

Table 5 Correlations between HRM practices, lean production practices, lean duration, operational performance and firm performance

	Mean	SD	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15
1 Work design	3.86	.61	.73														
2 Supervision	3.81	.63	.708**	.76													
3 Knowledge sharing	3.83	.59	.714**	.721**	.73												
4 Job-related training	3.70	.68	.651**	.634**	.685**	.75											
5 Talent management	3.72	.63	.717**	.634**	.722**	.645**	.77										
6 Waste minimization	3.71	.67	.134**	.261**	.275**	.265**	.239**	.77									
7 Continuous improvement	3.57	.69	.269**	.266**	.358**	.312**	.314**	.712**	.76								
8 Defects minimization	3.68	.61	.274**	.290**	.352**	.307**	.352**	.666**	.698**	.81							
9 JIT and pull	3.75	.64	.391**	.390**	.315**	.382**	.391**	.711**	.715**	.722**	.76						
10 Cross functional teams	3.46	.72	.375**	.312**	.370**	.307**	.392**	.580**	.648**	.558**	.669**	.77					
11 Employee involvement	3.53	.66	.362**	.307**	.392**	.338**	.321**	.626**	.658**	.599**	.660**	.710**	.77				
12 Information availability	3.76	.52	.344**	.368**	.381**	.314**	.345**	.595**	.687**	.652**	.671**	.656**	.622**	.74			
13 Lean duration (yrs)	4.87	1.37	.438**	.413**	.559**	.348**	.437**	.475**	.453**	.539**	.564**	.469**	.503**	.426**	-		
14 Operational performance	3.60	.58	.320**	.309**	.382**	.310**	.321**	.310**	.361**	.361**	.343**	.383**	.395**	.395**	.408**	.75	
15 Firm performance	3.86	.63	.450**	.397**	.406**	.330**	.391**	.355**	.378**	.404**	.423**	.331**	.369**	.383**	.438**	.637**	.72

Notes: **p < 0.01; diagonal entries, square root of AVE; off-diagonal entries, correlations between constructs

Table 6. Results of model comparisons

Model	χ^2/df	CFI	TLI	RMSEA
1 HRM practices -> lean production practices -> operational performance -> firm performance (H3)	3.204	.924	.905	.059
2 HRM practices -> operational performance -> firm performance	2.806	.909	.883	.080
3 HRM practices -> lean production practices	2.017	.911	.887	.073
4 Lean production practices -> operational performance -> firm performance (H2)	3.007	.941	.927	.068
5 Lean production practices -> operational performance (H1)	2.789	.973	.959	.065
6 HRM practices -> firm performance	2.239	.969	.946	.081

Table 7. Results from PROCESS

Predictor variable	Firm performance		
	B(SE)	LL 95% CI	UL 95% CI
HRM practices	.397(.11)***		
Lean production practices	.357(.13)***		
Operational performance	.345(.07)***		
R ²	.577***		
<hr/>			
Bootstrapped indirect effect:	B(SE)	LL 95% CI	UL 95% CI
HRM practices -> lean production practices -> operational performance -> firm performance	.152(.04)***	.169	.256

Notes: LL = lower limit; CI = confidence interval; UL = upper limit. Unstandardized regression coefficients are reported; standard errors (SE) are in parentheses. Bootstrap sample size = 5,000. ***p<.001 (two-tailed)

Table 8. Results of model comparisons

Model	χ^2/df	CFI	TLI	RMSEA
1 Hypothesised model	4.431	.901	.855	.054
2 Model 1 ^a	4.844	.892	.806	.056
3 Model 2 ^b	4.373	.805	.759	.059

Notes:

^aIn comparison to hypothesised model, Model 1 places lean duration between lean production practices and operational performance.

^bModel 2 places lean duration between operational performance and firm performance.

Appendix 1 – Item measures

HRM Practices

(1 = strongly disagree, 5 = strongly agree; Cronbach's alpha = 0.704; KMO sampling adequacy = 0.876; Bartlett's χ^2 and significance = 32.21, $p < 0.001$; total variation explained = 72.96; $n = 1189$)

Shop-floor work design helps to obtain good performance from employees
Employees have access to tools and techniques that need to be effective
Employees aware how they expect to contribute to the organization's success
Employees have access to resources (such as materials) that need to be effective
Effective systems are in place to store information that are shared among employees
Effective systems are in place to share information among employees
Continuously reviews and updates best practices on knowledge sharing
Employees trust their team members to get the job done
Effective systems are in place to collect information from employees
Better utilization of existing knowledge within employees to make thoughtful decisions at work
Employees are provided with resources (including time) for knowledge sharing
Constantly makes job related training a priority
Training programmes provided to employees are relevant to their job tasks
A system is in place to provide information to make decisions regarding training programmes
Constantly evaluates the effectiveness of training programmes provided for employees
Employees are well trained on work processes
Immediate supervisors are honest in communications
Immediate supervisors facilitate to eliminate barriers to effective work
Employees trust supervisor's ability in leading to achieve set objectives
Immediate supervisors are open in communication
Immediate supervisors constantly demonstrate core values of the organization
A system is in place to fill vacancies with qualified internal candidates
A system is in place to recognize achievements of employees
A system is in place to retain good performers
A system is in place to identify key performers

Lean production practices

(1 = strongly disagree, 5 = strongly agree; Cronbach's alpha = 0.716; KMO sampling adequacy = 0.691; Bartlett's χ^2 and significance = 27.54, $p < 0.001$; total variation explained = 69.35; $n = 1189$)

Lot sizes are maintained at the minimum possible level
Machine set-up times are maintained at the minimum possible level
Machine down time is maintained at the minimum possible level
Value of rework in relation to export orders is maintained at the minimum possible level
Value of waste in relation to export orders is maintained at the minimum possible level
Value of work in progress is maintained at the minimum possible level
Problems leading to defects are identified promptly to prevent occurrences of defects in the production line
Sources of defects are identified promptly through constant monitoring of production process
Defective parts (machine error) are identified promptly to take corrective action
Employees concern to manufacture fault free items
Rework area is maintained at the minimum possible level
Defective items (human error) are identified promptly to take corrective action
Performance of teams are being assessed using multiple criteria (such as quality and lead times)
Employees are given training on different functional areas (such as maintenance and quality control)
Employees are provided with leadership training for effective team working
Employees are given training on different tasks
Sufficient amount of training is given to newly hired employees to orient them to cross functional team work
Each employee rotates across different tasks in the shop-floor
Suggestions provided by employees had been implemented promptly
Employees actively involved in providing suggestions for continuous improvement
On the spot problem solving is in operation in an effective manner
Quality teams are operating in an effective manner
A formal employee suggestion scheme is operating in an effective manner
Amount of materials scheduled through backward requests is maintained at the maximum possible level

Usage of backward requests in the material flow is maintained at the maximum possible level
Amount of time spent in processing each order is maintained at the minimum possible level
Employees are provided with right parts, in the right quantity at the right point in time
Regular meetings are held to discuss information of the shop-floor with employees
Employees are provided with relevant information of the shop-floor regularly
Employees are provided with information of strategic nature (such as short and long term goals of the firm) constantly
Employees are provided with information about performance of different functional areas of the shop-floor
Employees are provided with relevant information of the shop-floor on time
Employees accept responsibility for their work in the shop-floor
Teams are assigned to perform supervisory tasks
Work content of teams have been broadened
Employees rotate team leadership among members in the team
Employees accept responsibility to perform tasks that span across different functional areas (such as maintenance and quality control)
Levels in the organization structure of the shop-floor is maintained at the minimum possible level

Operational performance

(1 = strongly disagree, 5 = strongly agree; Cronbach's alpha = 0.790; KMO sampling adequacy = 0.751; Bartlett's χ^2 and significance = 21.54, $p < 0.001$; eigenvalue = 2.46; explained variation = 61.51; $n = 1189$)

Floor space saving
Delivery in full on time
Efficiency of the process
Raw material on time delivery
Efficiency of machine operators
First time through inspection
Accepted quality level at the end of the line

Firm performance

(1 = strongly disagree, 5 = strongly agree; Cronbach's alpha = 0.800; KMO sampling adequacy = 0.763; Bartlett's χ^2 and significance = 23.53, $p < 0.001$; eigenvalue = 2.52; explained variation = 63.08; $n = 1189$)

Level of productivity of my organization compared to other firms in the industry
Long-run profitability of my organization compared to other firms in the industry
Growth prospect in exports of my organization compared to other firms in the industry
Good will of my organization compared to other firms in the industry

Appendix 2 HRM practices

Item	Work design	Knowledge sharing	Job-related training	Supervision	Talent management
Shop-floor work design helps to obtain good performance from employees	.756				
Employees have access to tools and techniques that need to be effective	.741				
Employees aware how they expect to contribute to the organization's success	.713				
Employees have access to resources (such as materials) that need to be effective	.711				
Effective systems are in place to store information that are shared among employees		.771			
Effective systems are in place to share information among employees		.759			
Continuously reviews and updates best practices on knowledge sharing		.753			
Employees trust their team members to get the job done		.746			
Effective systems are in place to collect information from employees		.723			
Better utilization of existing knowledge within employees to make thoughtful decisions at work		.712			
Employees are provided with resources (including time) for knowledge sharing		.700			
Constantly makes job related training a priority			.798		
Training programmes provided to employees are relevant to their job tasks			.780		
A system is in place to provide information to make decisions regarding training programmes			.753		
Constantly evaluates the effectiveness of training programmes provided for employees			.732		
Employees are well trained on work processes			.701		
Immediate supervisors are honest in communications				.819	
Immediate supervisors facilitate to eliminate barriers to effective work				.789	
Employees trust supervisor's ability in leading to achieve set objectives				.750	
Immediate supervisors are open in communication				.724	
Immediate supervisors constantly demonstrate core values of the organization				.719	
A system is in place to fill vacancies with qualified internal candidates					.792
A system is in place to recognize achievements of employees					.775
A system is in place to retain good performers					.773
A system is in place to identify key performers					.721
Cronbach's alpha	.80	.85	.86	.87	.86
AVE	.53	.54	.57	.58	.59
Construct reliability	.82	.89	.87	.87	.85

Employees are provided with information about performance of different functional areas of the shop-floor							.732
Employees are provided with relevant information of the shop-floor on time							.721
Employees accept responsibility for their work in the shop-floor							.788
Teams are assigned to perform supervisory tasks							.781
Work content of teams have been broadened							.757
Employees rotate team leadership among members in the team							.747
Employees accept responsibility to perform tasks that span across different functional areas (such as maintenance and quality control)							.746
Levels in the organization structure of the shop-floor is maintained at the minimum possible level							.717
Cronbach's alpha	.83	.89	.84	.87	.84	.86	.88
AVE	.59	.65	.60	.58	.58	.55	.59
Construct reliability	.90	.92	.90	.87	.85	.86	.89

Appendix 4 Operational performance

Item	Operational performance
Floor space saving (m ²)	.789
Delivery in full on time (DIFOT) (%)	.774
Efficiency of the process (%)	.767
Raw material on time delivery (%)	.735
Efficiency of machine operators (%)	.726
First time through (FIT) inspection (%)	.721
Accepted quality level (AQL) (%) at the end of the line	.714
Cronbach's alpha	.79
AVE	.56
Construct reliability	.90

Appendix 5 Firm performance

Item	Firm performance
Level of productivity of my organization compared to other firms in the industry	.760
Long-run profitability of my organization compared to other firms in the industry	.721
Growth prospect in exports of my organization compared to other firms in the industry	.710
Good will of my organization compared to other firms in the industry	.704
Cronbach's alpha	.80
AVE	.52
Construct reliability	.81